
The Existence of Diffused Transcendental Elements as an Avenue of Human Wisdom in Paulo Coelho's *The Alchemist*

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Keywords:

*Dreams, Intuitions,
Transcendental elements*

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14102134

ABSTRACT

Paulo Coelho's literary works are deeply influenced by his personal experiences, dreams, and spiritual beliefs. This study explores the role of dreams and intuitions in Coelho's life and how they shape his novels, particularly *The Alchemist*. Coelho's belief in the power of dreams and the language of the soul, which he perceives as the language of God expressed through intuitions, is a central theme in his works. Despite facing personal struggles and being sent to a mental hospital during his adolescence, Coelho's experiences served as a source of inspiration for his writing. His novels convey a message of hope, perseverance, and the realization of one's innate potential through the pursuit of dreams. *The Alchemist* exemplifies Coelho's philosophy, as the protagonist, Santiago, embarks on a journey to fulfill his dreams, guided by his intuitions and the universal elements. The current research focuses on the author's presentation of these universal elements and intuitions in this novel as they convey profound meaning. In this study, the paper explores the presence of transcendental elements that are diffused in this world and their relationship with Human life in association with the ultimate truth that exists beyond the human realm.

Introduction

Coelho's works emphasize the importance of self-confidence and the existential strategy needed to survive and succeed. This study highlights the profound impact of Coelho's personal beliefs and experiences on his literary creations, which continue to inspire readers worldwide to follow their dreams and trust in the power of intuition. According to the transcendence philosophy, humans are both the creators of and receptors of meaning from the spiritual world through intuition. Hence, in Coelho's *The Alchemist*, the events, incidents, and happenings have meanings to convey. With their intuitions, human beings can receive meaning and create meaning to enrich their life with the guidance of ultimate truth.

Methodology

The general objective of the proposed research paper is to manifest the intimate and profound relationship between the Universe and human life. Coelho has delineated this concept by searching for a shepherd boy to accomplish his dreams, which most people find difficult. 2. The study also presents the omnipresence of universal elements, which is closely associated with the transformation of the protagonist on his way to his quest, which is similar to the notion of transcendental ideas of Individualism and Humanism.

The research work is divided into two primary and secondary sources. The primary source of the research paper is from *The Alchemist* novel, and the secondary source comprises library and internet resources.

Discussion

Our dreams result from inspiration, yearning, and love. Dreams are impulses with a definite goal in life. Hence, dreams are not taught or created; they are a realization of innate potential. Life becomes meaningful when pursuing dreams. It becomes contented when our dreams are achieved, which is life's ultimate satisfaction and joy when one follows their dreams and achieves them in one day. How many people realize our dreams? How many people pursue our dreams? Unfortunately, the answer is disappointing, as few people are fortunate enough to follow their dreams. Why do we forget our dreams? Alternatively, do only a few have dreams to follow? All creations are at liberty to dream at a young age; the sky is the limit, and they have and have infinite dreams. Over time, they have been influenced by external forces, begin to move with the peripheral current and forget their dreams.

Men are motivated to pursue a career, earn money, and live comfortably. Hence, the burial of personalized dreams before adulthood has become common. After that, the focus was not on dreams but on money. Money provides material satisfaction but not the satisfaction of the soul. When people live for themselves, they live their dreams. They become the passion of one's life. A passionate chase of dreams makes one strong with perseverance and determination. Dreams create strong individuals. The integrity within inspires and, later, creates inspiration. Hence, life transforms into life with a purpose. Great people, who all remain an inspiration, lived a life with a purpose. The purpose is the realization of humanity within each. People with a purpose in life never give up, withdraw, or compromise. They leave an impact, and such an impact reconstructs others. Purpose renders perfect satisfaction to the soul. We become closer to God. So many legends made their life the epitome of purpose- Mother Teresa, Nelson Mandela, and Martin Luther King to Mahatma Gandhi.

Paulo Coelho, the most acclaimed writer of the century, is well known for his optimistic perception of life. Coelho's works are stuffed with mysteries and miracles of life. Paulo Coelho's keen desire for travel, exploration, and belief in spiritual enlightenment is manifested in his novels. Coelho's experience serves as an abundant source of literary writing. His inspiration and experience are reflected in his characters and plots. He expanded his vision and perception of the world and life. His vision has the highest degree of positivism. Coelho's world is full of hope, love, and a quest for knowledge and experience. In the Research report on "A Psychobiographical Study of Intuition on a Writer's Life: Paulo Coelho Revisited," Claude Helen Mayer and David Maree state the struggles overcome by Coelho from Encyclopedia Britannica as:

During adolescence Coelho was sent to a mental hospital three times by his parents because he did not comply with his parents expectations and due to the fact that he just wanted to become a successful writer at any cost... He changed his life radically at the age of 36 years after a pilgrimage to Santiago de Compostela in Spain, when he experienced a spiritual awakening and felt inspired to write the book *The Pilgrimage* (Coelho, 1987).

Britannica defines Transcendence as “an interpretation of the divine, which is Transcendence and immanence; each is meant to express the relation between the divine and finite realities” . Transcendence means going beyond a limit or surpassing a boundary; immanence means remaining within or existing within the confines of a limit. The divine is said to transcend humanity. The notion of Transcendence is prevalent in Coelho's works, which are expressions of hope and success despite

disparities in any form. Life has the essence and beauty of living with hope. Coelho's works have underlying thoughts. Coelho's belief in spiritualism is a precise manifestation of perseverance that strives toward success by achieving one's dreams. Undoubtedly, this has become the core concept of Coelho's novels.

Paulo Coelho reveals the influence of dreams and intuitions in his life. He closely associates himself with his dreams, intuitions, and spiritual beliefs to move on in life's journey, which has made his life successful. Since childhood, Coelho followed his dreams and even experienced a chaotic experience of madness to actualize his dreams. Coelho's insane experiences hardly influenced him but instead created inner strength within him. Coelho's works convey a strong message to the world deprived of spiritual values and self-confidence that an individual must imbibe an existential strategy to survive successfully. His works, namely *The Alchemist*, *The Valkyries*, *By the River Piedra, I sat down and wept*, *Veronica Decides to Die*. His significant characters realize their potential and learn the secrets of life through their journey and experience, ultimately actualizing them.

In his personal life, Coelho experiences frustration and failure. These frustrations and failures returned him to his childhood beliefs about Christianity and God. He rationally realized his intuitive feelings and profound relatedness to his dreams. He realizes the power of intuition. He understood that the language of the soul is the language of God, which is expressed through intuition. Coelho's belief in intuition was absolute; hence, he comprehended it through multiple objects, events, symbols, and signs. His works are strongly constructed around these beliefs. *The Alchemist* manifests Coelho's belief in institutions and the soul's language.

The novel *The Alchemist* is about a shepherd boy determined to follow his dreams. He believes in a spiritual connection to his dreams. His dreams directed him to a treasure in the faraway land of Egypt. The hero, Santiago, trusts the role of universal elements in one's life. His pursuit of the treasure led him to recognize the existence of fundamental principles that are prevalent across all domains. His perseverance in moving toward his legend brings about his actualization and innate potential. "It's the possibility of having a dream come true that makes life interesting, he thought, as he looked again at the position of the sun, and hurried his pace." (10 TA)

Paulo Coelho insists on the validity of having a personal legend in life to make it meaningful and worthy through the life of Santiago in *The Alchemist*. Having a personal legend and pursuing it with determination and perseverance reflects Coelho's life. Santiago is constantly searching for a purposeful

life, further motivated by recurrent dreams that haunt his sleep. In his dream vision, he saw a child inviting him to the Pyramid of Egypt to discover a hidden treasure. According to Sonia Soni in her article, "Life Realized through Riddles: A Study of Paulo Coelho's *The Alchemist*":

Coelho's *The Alchemist* has been hailed as a book that has transformed the lives of millions of people for the better. It is more a self-help book than a novel. In it, Coelho has focused on the art of living – how to make life enjoyable by following one's dream. He asserts that one must discover one's legend or the very purpose of being. Santiago's courage opens doors to his inner self.

Santiago was determined to pursue his dreams; he sought his father's support and permission to follow his dreams. Initially, his father refused but later acknowledged him to go as he had personal legends to follow in his youth, which his parents and society curbed. Santiago began his journey with courage and determination. His multifarious experiences motivated him to accomplish his dreams and gain life wisdom. His journey towards his goal is the epitome of man's journey towards goals and success in life. Coelho's credence in spirituality vividly manifests itself in Santiago's journey toward his dream. Coelho connects all elements, events, and people throughout the novel with the ultimate universal power. He confidently expresses the integral eminence of universal power that exists unconsciously in abundance. Universal elements play a vital role in the process and existence of the world and individual life. Coelho's life as a writer after his spiritual experience of walking 500-plus miles on the road of Santiago de Compostela in northwestern Spain marked his belief in pantheism. He wrote his first novel, *The Pilgrimage*, following the incident.

Transcendental Elements

Santiago's encounters with people, omens, and nature have provided great life lessons. His observations and perceptions were positive; hence, they positively influenced him. Santiago is definite in his purpose and pragmatically relates his meetings, dreams, and events to it. Santiago's meeting with the king proved this. Since meeting with the King of Salem, his belief in God, God's plan, and his life and journey have taken a spiritual perspective. He experiences positive, proper communication through omens and signs that he comes across. He comprehends the secrets and mysteries of life from him; he realizes his true purpose and goal only after his encounter with King Melchizedek. Paulo Coelho emphasizes the role of the Universe and the power of transcendental elements that collaborate in an individual's success.

It prepares your spirit and your will, because there is one great truth on this planet: whoever you are, or whatever it is that you do, when you really want something, it's because that desire originated in the soul of the Universe. It's your mission on earth"... "And, when you want something, all the Universe conspires in helping you to achieve it (21)

Coelho's confidence in the universal connection between Man and God is manifested through fragmented events in the novel. The transcendental elements serve as guiding stars and are revealed as Omens. They are visible and understood at an intuitive level of consciousness. Profoundly, they exist within the subconscious minds of humans. Indeed, they direct the soul if they are correctly comprehended at the right time. "In order to find the treasure, you will have to follow the omens. God has prepared a path for everyone to follow. You just have to read the omens that he left for you".(28)

Santiago's encounter with the crystal merchant reveals the significance of Santiago's faith and confidence in the omens. Since he met with the crystal merchant, it has only been a story of success and growth for the Merchant. Of course, Santiago's positivism and belief in the king's words made him believe in universal power. " It's called the Principle of favourability, beginner's Luck. Because life wants you to achieve your destiny". (50) Santiago, with his positivism, transformed the life and business of the crystal merchant. He makes an impression on the Merchant's mind; nevertheless, he helps him realize the value of dreams and life opportunities. He focuses on his dreams: his ideas about the Merchant reveal Santiago's determinism and perseverance, stuffed with hope. "I want to get back to my sheep faster. We have to take advantage when luck is on our side, and do as much to help it as its doing to help us. It's called the principle of favourability. Or beginner's luck". (51)

Santiago's conversation with his beloved Fathima demonstrates his belief in a universal power. His conversation with the caravan driver and Alchemist reveals profound truths about life and the Universe. Despite all these, Santiago realized the ultimate power of the soul of the Universe when he became one with the wind." The boy reached through the soul of the world, and saw that it was a part of the soul of God. And he saw that that the soul of the God was his own soul. And that he , a boy, could perform miracles." (145)

Conclusion

Paulo Coelho's novels, mainly *The Alchemist*, implicitly manifest the existence, power, and connection of the Universal elements with the world. He brings the limitations of mortal versus the

ultimate power of the Universe. Paulo Coelho's strong belief in the connection and guidance of the Universal power is inevitably a kind of experience that undoubtedly anyone with a spiritual perspective will have attained. Hence, Coelho and his novels are beyond the limitations of literature and life; they are towards a mission and a purpose.

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